

Common Error in Depreciation Computation

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ABSTRACT

Depreciation is one of the significant factor to be considered in the financial statements. It provides to recover the cost of the asset over the life of the asset. While computing depreciation one should mind useful life of the asset, nature of the asset, method of depreciation and existing statutory requirements. Many may not be ware of underlying complications while calculating depreciation. To be more precise in case of reducing balance method many are considering inappropriate rate of depreciation. One should be cautious about the statutory requirements, which might lead to regrets.

1. Introduction

One of the main reasons for calculating depreciation is to recovery of the cost that is incurred on fixed assets over their useful life. There are other reasons like considering wear and tear, matching periodical expenses with concerned periodical incomes and etc. Useful life of assets vary from one asset to other. In India useful life of assets for companies has been specified by the Companies Act 2013. Earlier act "Companies act 1956" specified the rate at which depreciation needs to be calculated. However in the new companies act only life of the asset and the maximum residual value of the assets has been specified and not the rate of depreciation or method of depreciation. My observation reveals that many people who are computing depreciation on "Written Down Value Method" or "Reducing Balance Method" committing error in calculating depreciation. Focus of this article will be on the error committing and what is the correct way of calculating depreciation under written down value method.

2. Review of the Accounting Concept of Depreciation

International Accounting Standard 8 (Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors) made overwhelming assertions on the conceptualization of depreciation and method of presentation in the financial statements. The assertions of IAS 8 notwithstanding, many Accountants are yet to decide whether Depreciation should be conceived as accounting policy or as accounting estimates. Each of these conceptions has a different effect on the Entities' performance presentation. This section of the paper will focus on the error reviewing the right way of calculating depreciation purpose, and different conception of depreciation.

3. Objective of the Study

The main objective of this paper is to review the what is the correct way of calculating depreciation under written down value method.

They specific objectives are to:

Identify the effects of theoretical and practical approaches in providing for depreciation on financial reports using the available methods under IAS 16 Property, Plant and Equipment issued by IASB.

Formula Explanation:

Change in life of assets has been specified in new companies' act 2013. However it does not suggested change in depreciation method. Hence there is no need to recalculate effect of depreciation from the period of asset inception for depreciation. Change in the life of assets is only a change in accounting estimate but not a change in accounting policy. And only Net value of the asset lying in the books need to be depreciated for the remaining period of asset life. Now we will understand the formula for reducing balance method.

The following formula is be used to calculate rate of depreciation under reducing balance method

$$\text{depreciation rate} = 1 - \sqrt[N]{\frac{\text{residual value}}{\text{cost of fixed asset}}}$$

Here "N" denotes for useful life of the asset.

The above formula is based on following two assumptions

1. Residual value is always more than zero.
2. Depreciation is calculated at equal periodical ends.

First assumption can be overcome by considering nominal value as residual value, which may not affect financial statements materially. In case of second assumption also it is possible to overcome unless life of the asset is not an integer value, if calculated manually.

Formula derivation

Basing on the assumptions of reducing balance method at the end of 1st year will be as below

$$\text{Written Down Value (W.D.V)} = (100\% - R\%)X$$

Where R = Rate of Depreciation
 C = Cost of the asset
 X = Multiply Symbol

$$\text{depreciation rate} = 1 - \sqrt[N]{\frac{\text{residual value}}{\text{cost of fixed asset}}}$$

W.D.V at the end of 2nd year will be as below
 $W.D.V = (100\% - R\%)^2XC$

W.D.V at the end of Nth year will be as below
 $W.D.V = (100\% - R\%)^NXC$

However at the end of Nth year it will be at Residual Value, hence

$$(100\% - R\%)^NXC = \text{Residual Value}$$

$$(100\% - R\%)^N = \text{Residual Value}/C$$

$$100\% - R\% = (\text{Residual Value}/C)^{1/N}$$

$$R\% = 100\% - (\text{Residual Value}/C)^{1/N}$$

Which is nothing but

However in case of assumption 2 above the following illustration method may be adopted although it was not accurate method to overcome material misstatements for all assets.

Date of asset capitalized and ready to use 01.03.2015

Capitalized value of asset (in Rupees)	1,00,000/-
Residual value (5%)	5000/-
Life of asset	3 years
Depreciation as per above method	63.16%

No. of days asset depreciable in the financial year 2014-15 = 31

Hence depreciation will be calculated as explained below by overcoming second assumption of the formula

	Rs.1,00,000 x 63.16%	63160.00		5364.27	Depreciation for 31 Days in 2014-15	
W.D.V	36840.00			7	15	
				57795.73	Balance Depreciation	
	Rs.36840 x 63.16%	23268.14			59766.53	Depreciation for 2015-16(366 Days)
W.D.V	13571.86			1970.80	31 days Depreciation	
				21297.34	Balance Depreciation	
					22025.38	Depreciation for 2016-17
	Rs.23,268.14 x 63.16%	8571.984		728.03	31 days Depreciation	
W.D.V	4999.87					
				7843.95	Balance Depreciation in 2017-18	

Depreciation for the financial year 2014-15 = Rs.1,00,000/- x 63.16% x 31/365 = 59,766.53

Depreciation for the financial year 2015-16 will be sum of the following two calculations

Depreciation 1 = Rs.1,00,000/- x 63.16% x (365-31)/365 = 57,795.73

Depreciation 2 = (Rs.1,00,000/- x (100%-63.16%)) x 63.16% x 31/366 = 1970.80

Hence total depreciation for financial year 2015-16 is = 57,795.73 + 1970.80

For the succeeding periods may also be calculated as indicated above.

Explanation of common error

The forthcoming example cases will explain the common errors, I have observed. If we calculate depreciation on Net asset value on 31.03.2015 (i.e Rs.1,00,000 – 5364.247 = 94,635.7530) @ 63.16% directly then at the end of life of the asset you will get more than Rs.5000/-. And such deviation from residual value required will depend on date of capitalization of asset. It can be explained in the following cases

Case 1:-

Date of Capitalise	01-04-14
Cost	100000
2014-15	63160
01.04.15	36840.00
2015-16	23268.14
01.04.16	13571.86
2016-17	8571.98

Case 2:-

Date of Capitalise	03-06-14
Cost	100000
for 302 days	52258.41
01.04.15	47741.59
2015-16	30153.59
01.04.16	17588
2016-17	11108.58

Case 3:-

Date of Capitalise	30-09-14
Cost	100000
for 183 days	31666.52
01-04-15	68333.48
2015-16	43159.43
01.04.16	25174.05
2016-17	15899.93

01.04.17	4999.87

01-04-17	6479.42
for 63 days	706.3597
02.06.17	5773.06

01-04-17	9274.121
for 182 days	2920.744
29-09-17	6353.378

As per my observation one will get maximum deviation when asset is capitalized on 30-09-14. For any asset capitalized on 30.09.14 we will get maximum deviation in the residual value because it was the date which got maximum number of days from either financial year beginning date or financial year ending date. This is due to change in the value at end of financial year on which rate of depreciation is applied.

Impact explanation

- Deviation from residual value than expected/required.
- It will result in violation of Companies Act 2013 whenever residual value exceeds 5%.
- It might result in incorrect profits calculation.
- It will result in calculation of incorrect minimum alternative tax as per section 115JB Income Tax Act 1961.
- It will result in computation of inaccurate profit/loss on sale of assets.
- Presentation inaccurate book value of assets and depreciation.

Solution for calculating accurate rate of depreciation

However I know how to resolve this problem which will be explained as below.

Companies Act 2013 doesn't specified the rate of depreciation but the life of asset. Hence we can calculate the appropriate rate for depreciation calculation in a method other than by using the formula specified in the first page of this article. We can get the rate appropriate rate by two solutions

Solution1 :-

Consider if asset is capitalized on 03-06-14
 Using 63.16% deviation we got from residual value
 = 5773.06 - 5000 = 773.06
 Using 70% deviation we will get
 = 1670.20 (calculated)
 Hence required rate of depreciation
 = $63.16 + \frac{773.06 * (70 - 63.16)}{773.06 + 1670.20}$
 = 63.16 + 2.1642
 = 65.3242%

In this method we will loss accuracy depending on number of digits we use after decimal points. This is the method generally used to calculate Internal Rate of Return

Solution-2:-

My preference is Solution-2 which is explained in below:
 In this method I use Microsoft Excel sheet for calculation which produces maximum accuracy possible than above solution-1. Observe the below picture

In the above picture I have calculated depreciation @70% for the asset capitalized on 03-06-14

Step 1:- While calculating depreciation by formula for the purpose of rate I have made reference to Cell Number C3 every time I have calculated.

Step 2:- After making calculation by formula as specified in above step we will get the values shown in picture, Then use

the option called "What if Analysis" and in that "Goal Seek" we will get this get this option in Tools of 2003 version also and the version used in the above is 2007.

Step3:- We will get the following picture and specify the values as shown in the picture

In the above picture I got \$C\$14 by selecting C14 cell have specified value of 5000 assuming that 5% of 1,00,000 is residual value. I got \$C\$3 by selecting C3 cell. Then press ok .Then it will recalculate and modify the rate to 65.07% which most accurate method that can be used by everybody

In case of old assets the following may be done

Take W.D.V value on 31.03.2014 as per books which is arrived by calculating in old rates specified in Companies Act 1956 in the place of Rs.100000/- specified in the above example. Then calculate it for the remaining period of life and arrive at residual value. And then apply the above specified solution-2 for more accuracy and get the required rate of depreciation.

However in some cases old assets remaining useful life will not be exactly in years but can also be some days or months in addition to complete years. In such cases also the method,

I have preferred will work but not the formula specified in the first page of this article.

If an asset like Buildings with RCC Frame structure having life 60 Years, it may lengthy procedure to arrive residual value following "Method 2". To arrive at residual value in less steps for any assets the following steps may be followed

Step 1

Calculate W.D.V for the first year in normal way
(i.e Rs.57917.81 in diagram explained in Excel above)

Step 2

$(W.D.V \text{ of Step 1})(100\% - R\%)(N-1)$

Step 3

Depreciation to be provided in last financial year = (Outcome of Step 2)(R%)(No of days of life in last financial of asset/No of Days in that financial Year)

Residual Value = Outcome of Step 2 (Less) Depreciation to be provided in last financial year

In the above calculation R% is rate of depreciation and "N" is life of asset in years

4. Conclusion

One need to be cautious while computing depreciation. Consider depreciation in appropriate way may result future penalties. Rate of depreciation considered could be wrong if one does not understand the explanation. For lesser value of assets, impact might negligible. The more the number of digits involved in the value of asset the more the material effect will be in the financial statements.

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